

Examination and Survival of Cultural Values in the Historical Texture: Camerino City-Italy and Turkey Trabzon City-Turkey

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Abstract: In this study, Camerino city and Trabzon city were asked to answer these concepts, since the historical values, their meanings, their learning, and their cultural values must be determined and preserved in order to protect the environment. For this purpose, the interpretation of old-new reconstruction together with imitation and contrast approach has been examined for the problem of "harmony" and "integration" which is one of the biggest problems encountered in today's historical environments. The research area is limited to Italy Camerino city and Turkey Trabzon site. In the study, sampling methods were used in direct Camerino and Trabzon cities. In both fields of study, proposals have been made for the analysis and evaluation of physical items qualified as historical documents and to ensure cultural continuity by interpretation of data.

Keywords: Historical environment, environmental design, re-evaluation, sustainability, culture, Camerino, Trabzon

1. INTRODUCTION

It determines the character of the cities, the spaces and the elements that make up the city. One of the most important of these can be said to be the settlement sites of historical value. Historical accumulation, which plays an important role in the formation of the identity of the cities, and thus the necessity of preserving the structure and its surroundings is needed.

The settlement areas that have been evolving since the first ages and the way of living in these areas have thus been interpreted differently in different societies. Societies with different cultures, traditions, and briefly different lifestyles have also differed in the form of construction-environment in which their lives can last. This is because the formation of the structural elements of the environment is affected in a negative way by the actions that the necessities require, the relations between the actions and the spaces with respect to the places, according to the way of life of each society. As a result of the negative factors that cause the urbanization to change and the sense of touch in the cities to change, the city's apparentness decreases and its continuity disappears. The change and development of cities can be said to be the inevitable way of a healthy society. However,

this path should not overlook the values of the past, but should look at the components in their formation. Thus, clarifying the information about the city's past makes it easier to find a clear path for the future.

The values and importance of historical environments are as follows;

- Ensure the readability of cities (emphasis and node points),
- Strong urban image and consistent integrity,
- History, time and future readability,
- They must be original,
- Symbolizing the city document and city,
- Symbolic value movements,
- Communities feel their history,
- put out old new attachments (harmony or opposition)
- Referencing historical events, places and structures,
- Ensure cultural continuity,
- Establish core points in the establishment of cities,
- The forms, arrangements, relations (typological values) and the inspiration for contemporary designs of the structures that the history reflects (Velioglu, 1992).

One of the biggest problems in today's historical environment is the problem of "harmony" and "integration". Often old-new construction together;

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- Interpretation,
- Just like imitation and
- Three approaches are mentioned as contrast (Eldem, 1992).

Today, in the cities with historical values, the protection of historical touch gradually disappears gradually, the concept of the site emerged with the definition of the texture, the research and registration problems to be done for the preservation of structures, and the protection is in certain imprecations (Çakarcan, 1989, Kultufan, 1994). In such cities, regional analyzes should be made and historical touch protection sustainability should be provided.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Field of work - Sample selection

As a study area, Camerino city in Italy and Trabzon city in Turkey were selected as the site of social, cultural and social values (Figure1, 2).

Figure 1. Camerino city in Italy

Figure 2. Trabzon historical settlement area in Turkey

2.2. Methods

As a first step in the research, a direct preliminary survey has been carried out on site in both Camerino

and Trabzon. During the preliminary investigation, physical detection was determined using the detection-documentation study method. Photography and observation techniques have been used in the physical detection of the current situation. In the analytical study phase; "Detection-documentation work" has been examined under two headings in terms of physical determinations.

- Physical detection; Photographs and observation techniques were used in the determinations made to determine the present situation. Observations;
 - on the building scale
 - the settlement scale.

In the building scale;

- Determination of the monumental structure of the building scale,
- Findings related to civil architectural examples in building scale;
 - Determinations of prestigious housing and
 - Were examined as determinations of existing residences that are not prime.

In settlement scale; The existing map, the zoning plan and the zoning plan for conservation were obtained. The boundaries of old-new constructions and streets were determined and depending on them, the existing structures with historic features and values deducted from photographs were removed.

Houses that have been worked naturally have undergone a process of change, eventually changing from physical to social. The way of life and the change of the users, the corrections and joints brought by them are reflected in the structure and surroundings, naturally the structure and the environment are deformed and some part more or less disappears with time. There are few survivors who came up to the present day and still remain intact.

Taking all these factors into consideration, the study attempted to determine whether the traditional houses and constructions and their surroundings were from the old sources (by asking the elderly owners and by searching the literature), and the obtained data were evaluated.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Camerino city-Italy

Camerino city is a residential area where the traditional touch is intense and the shape of its core in history. The city of Camerino is located in the Marche Region, in the Appennine Mountains in the center of Italy. Chienti is in a pleasant position on the back which separates the valley of the river and the Potenza with its panoramic view. The old city center has undergone very little change over the past few

centuries, preserving its architectural richness. The city has been going on since the Neolithic period. This city, BC. After signing the alliance with Rome in 309, it became a thriving Roman city. Then, under the direction of Charlesmagne, Appennians became the capital of the Marca region, extending to the sea. City, allied with the Guelph and Manfredi empire was destroyed in 1259 by the troops. Later this year, the city's Signoria Varano 1200-1539 under management, grew artistic and commercial sense. Giulio Cesare Varano manager of the latter was dethroned in 1502 by Cesare Borgia, it was cut during this period that the political and cultural vitality. However, Guilio's son Giovonn Maria seized control of the city in 1503 and took the title of duke.

Most of the structures in the camarino are of the Varano family, 14-16. Built during the centuries of enlightened administration, attracting artists and academics. In 1545 the city was again under the papal rule. Until the merger of Italy, it was one of the main cities of the pope. A narrow street takes you from your accommodation to the main square Piazza Cavour, surrounded by the cathedral, the Archbishop's Palace, and the Ducal Palace, now a law school. All of them have been watching the statue of Pope Sistus V since 1587.

Camerino's historic settlement has been up to date as an "Old Town" site surrounded by castle walls shaped by topography. The old city is important with its harmonious layout, architectural integrity, and the streets that can protect its installations. Urban function is evaluated as housing and trade.

Religious structures, grave memorials, functional buildings, and monumental, totally functioning objects of everyday life are valued as a component of social history and are included in the scope of protection (See. Figures: Perspectives from the historical settlement of Camerino –Italy)

3.2 Trabzon city-Turkey

3.2.1 Findings related to the monumental structure in the structure scale: "Walls" are at the beginning of monumental constructions. A large part of them are the old buildings of the standing city walls. It was developed during the Byzantine period and repaired during the Ottoman period. It covers a very large area and extends from south to north; Upper Fortress (Inner Fortress), Ortahisar and Lower Fortress (North Fortress). The western part of the Pazarkapi neighborhood is surrounded by the walls called Lower Hisar. The walls are made of stone, and the walls are made of stone. There is the "Debris Gate" which opens to the port in the north. Since the establishment of this department, the city has become a center for commercial life, houses such as han,

hamam, and shop. Another monumental structure is the "Eight Direkt Hamam". The "Naked Mosque (St. Andrew)" located on the eastern border of the study area was previously church, and after conquest it was turned into a gallery.

3.2.2 Findings of examples of civil architecture in building scale: Housing and trade dominate the study area. Within the reconstruction plan, 21 houses and 1 hamam in the study area are registered as registered.

In the findings obtained about the houses; Registered houses and other residences. Historical houses; Ottoman style, Greek style and hybrid style. Wood and stone materials are used in the buildings. The number of floors is 2-3 floors. Generally, the facades are not open to the street. Especially ground floors are kept closed with garden-garden walls caused by the concept of privacy. The ground floor has a storage room, a kitchen and a winter room, a living room and bedrooms on the second floor, and a bedroom on the third floor. The exit from the buildings was seen as the exit during the structure, the exit in the middle of the building, and the exit along the two façades. However, there have been some examples.

Other unregistered buildings; New constructions, structures that are harmonious with the surrounding area, structures that do not fit the surrounding area that have lost the stylistic feature. As a result of the examinations carried out, it has been observed that the characteristics of historical touch, together with structural formation, proportions and items, are not capable of maintaining a healthy, harmonious and cultural identity with the old. Examples of physical, formal, material distortions that do not fit the surroundings in structures that do not fit the surrounding area.

3.3 Determination of Settlement Scale: Transportation in settlement scale, green, empty area, street, street walls, street elements, road pavements etc. It was investigated.

The fact that the streets are narrow and inclined causes only the possibility of pedestrian access and the difficulty of vehicle traffic. It is generally stone-faced and inclined. The ground floors of the structures located on the edges of the streets and the rubble stone brickwork attached to them take organic texture together with the tile and green garden walls. There are also staircase passages. Electric masts and wires are in the streets, which are conventional wire breakers. The discipline had to be placed in a separate plane, in the garden, adjacent to it, but the fact that there were gardens in the rear ensured that there was green in the settlement. Green is located in residential

gardens and garden walls. There is no social activity in the neighborhood. There is no collective challenge in the neighborhood.

4. DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Cities; Physically composed of individual and social spheres. The society that uses these areas has its own rules in economic, political, socio-cultural relations. Therefore, there is a close relationship between the social structure and the physical structure of the city. And the differences in the social structure cause differences in the structures. Based on the Camerino city example in urban improvement, the improvement proposal for the Trabzon site area has been developed.

4.1 Recommendations for improvement in the area of Trabzon site protection

The boundaries of the developed conservation project have been determined by the sodka gate street in the north, Hatip Cami street in the east, Zilver street, Zilver street in the south and Kudupoglu street. The silhouettes and suggestions about streets include 'Zilver Street, Kudupoglu street and Kenanoglu street'. When the conformity of the existing buildings to the materials mentioned in the Conservation Development Plan Legend is examined, it is seen that there is negative construction. These;

- The majority of recent structures are built as flat roofs.
- Marble tiles have been used in existing roof manufacturing.
- The building is not generally made of fringe. Some structures were found to have 15-20cm parapets.
- Window measurements are much larger or smaller than desired.
- Buildings are generally neglected and devastated. Physical, formal and material degradation were encountered.
- Maintenance or restoration of individual structures is attempted, but no improvement work has been found on the whole of the street.
- Construction of 4 to 5 storey buildings was permitted as well as not conforming to the 3 storey level of the protection development plan.

As a result of the examinations, it has been determined that the whole of the houses should be maintained and repaired. Findings made in the study area are processed on maps. Topics covered in maps; Spatial distribution of building protection ratings (good, medium, poor), spatial distribution of the protection status of the settlement (registered-registered buildings, structures that are not compatible with the surrounding area, Spatial restraint, moderate restoration, light restoration, integration, facade dressing, cleaning, demolition and

reconstruction), the spatial distribution of the building floor (two, three, , Four, five stories), material types (wood, stone, wood + stone, concrete), roof shapes (cradle, crushing, flat), (See. Figures: Perspectives from the historical settlement of Trabzon –Turkey).

In the study, the existing texture supported by the photographs taken from the streets is explained besides the processing of the data by the maps.

4.2 Proposal for protection Project

These structures belonging to a period when our society is abandoning in terms of social life are made to be suitable for today's conditions and it is a matter that is not considered by the planners yet and the enlightenment of the Supreme Council of Monuments which takes decisions about the restoration, The fact that the information and details are not given to private property owners, puts the future of these structures in danger. This increases the damage that the already unconscious user has caused to the construction.

The residence, which is the current function of the buildings in the vicinity, is designed as residential area because it is also suitable in today's conditions. Because the streets that characterize historic touches are narrow, vehicle traffic is difficult to make. In order to protect the characteristics, it is suggested to use streets to be flooded and closed to traffic but only for emergency service. Thus, Zilver Street, Kenanoglu Street, Kudupoglu Street was pedestrianized. Traffic Avni Housing Street, Hatip Mosque Street and Sotka Gate Street. The streets are covered with stone, only a part of Kenanoglu Street is covered with concrete. A new arrangement has been introduced in that area with floor covering. The street, which is an urban space, is also used as a private space for street residents. It is proposed to clean and reconstruct different parts of the garden walls located on the side of the street. Instead of electric poles that distort street silhouettes, lighting items that are installed in houses are proposed.

As a result of the examinations, all the houses in the streets have to be maintained and repaired. The types of intervention that are considered necessary are;

- Light Restoration; Restoration of facade plumbing, whitening
- Medium Restoration; Renovation of facade elements, windows, doors, repair of garden walls
- Complementation; Come on, console. Restructuring of these elements of structures that lose their elements
- Facade Dressing
- Cleaning; Subsequent removal of added parts

It has been seen that there are no social activities in the study area. Kudupoğlu Sokağın Hatip Cami Two old traditional houses in the corner where the mosque merges with the streets were proposed as a picnic where people gathered together. It is suggested that the empty space where the timber is built is opposite to the mosque located to the west of Hatip Cami Street.

From the past to the future, in the historical process, social economy etc. , Pazarkapi district, which has been able to protect its historical features partly or even, continues to function as a residential area as it is today. Despite the historical characteristics of the area, the user and the irritants that arise as a result of time factor, the visual pollution that occurs for this area disturbs the significance of the streets. However, such areas are the core points that show the prominence and continuity of cities.

Cultural values determined by historical touch (symbolic values in terms of form, order, etc.) should be determined, old and new building textures should be designed together and given necessary functions, and city equipments should be created by taking advantage of historical motifs. Historical

reconstruction should be achieved by installing new functions.

Liveings of the structures that are the demonstrations of the cultures and their transfer to the future are of great importance in terms of the historical continuity of the cities. For this purpose, conservation studies should be carried out, analysis and evaluation of physical items qualified as historical documents should be made and new designs should be made by interpreting the obtained data.

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Perspectives from the historical settlement of Camerino –Italy

Perspectives from the historical settlement of Trabzon -Turkey

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